

Team Contributions to the Alliance in FIRST Robotics Competitions

Jake Tan¹

¹Wissahickon High School, 521 Houston Rd, Ambler, PA 19002

Abstract

FIRST Robotics Competition (FRC) is an international high school robotics competition. At each competition event, there is a qualification round, followed by a playoff round. During the qualification round, each team is scored and ranked. Top seeded teams then pick two other teams to organize into alliances to compete in the playoff round. The contributions of the alliance captain, the 1st pick, and the 2nd pick to the alliance's probability of winning in the playoff round are evaluated using the data from eight competition events that Team 341, Miss Daisy attended during 2022 and 2023 seasons. Insights from this data exploration may help inform team's alliance selection strategy for future competitions.

Key Words: logistic regression, AIC, generalized linear model, robotics competition.

1. Introduction

FIRST Robotics Competition (FRC) is a high school level international robotics competition. To encourage cooperation as well as competition, each match is played between two alliances (blue versus red), and each alliance consists of three robots/teams. There are two parts to each FRC competition event. First, there is a qualifying round, in which each team is assigned to an alliance for each match in round robin style, where every team will encounter every other team at least once although they may be on the same alliance. Each team earns the scores that their alliance earned in the match. At the end of qualifying round, each team is ranked according to their "ranking points", earned by winning qualification rounds and completing specific in-game objectives. The eight highest scored teams become the captains for the alliances that will compete in the playoff round. They take turns to name their 1st pick, by descending captain rank, then their 2nd pick, by ascending rank, for their playoff alliances.

Within the FRC community, there are discussions on how to pick alliance partners. The purpose of this study is to explore the data from a total of eight competition events (over two competition seasons) in which my high school robotics team, Team 341, Miss Daisy, participated in 2022 and 2023. Six out of the eight were regional competition events in the FIRST Mid-Atlantic (FMA) District: Hatboro-Horsham Event, Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event, and District Championship for both years. The other two competition events were Division level competitions (Turing Division for 2022 and Hopper Division for 2023) at FIRST World Championship in which Team 341 also competed.

1.1 Performance Metrics

There are two performance metrics that are widely used in the FRC community. The first metric is Offensive Power Rating ([OPR](#)), which is a least square solution to the set of linear equations that adds up each team's OPR to the total score that the alliance earned at each match. The second metric is Expected Points Added ([EPA](#)), which is a modification of the Elo rating system used in evaluation of chess players. The EPA model is designed to predict the score of a match. Both performance metrics are used to represent the inherent strength of each robot/team.

1.2 Data Sources

The official competition lineup and score data from those eight competition events, as well as the OPR data, were obtained from the website [The Blue Alliance](#). The EPA data were calculated by and obtained from the website [Statbotics](#).

2. Data Visualization

2.1 Rapid React: 2022 Season

[Rapid React](#) was the 2022 season game. The basic goal of the game is to carry and shoot “cargo” (balls) into low or high “hubs”.

Figure 1 below is consisted of plots of EPA vs OPA of all the teams in the four competition events. The three district level events (Hatboro-Horsham Event, Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event, and District Championship) are in Week 1, 3, and 6 of the 2022 competition seasons. The World Championship (Turing Division) happened on Week 8. Different color dots represent the teams that are alliance captain, the 1st pick, the 2nd pick, and the teams that didn't make the playoff round.

It is interesting to note that the OPA and EPA scores are largely correlated with each other. As the competition season progresses, both OPA and EPA shifted upward, which may suggest improvement of teams' performance with more experience. For the District Championship and World Championship, the upward shift may also reflect selection bias since only teams with highest district level rankings can advance into the championship events. In general, the OPA and EPA of the alliance captains are not that different from those of the 1st picks, except that there seems to be individual team that dominated in earlier events.

Figure 2 below plots the probability of winning by the red alliance versus the performance metrics (OPR or EPA) of alliance captains, the 1st picks, and the 2nd picks. For each panel/event, the first row are plots for both the red captains and blue captains, with OPR plots on the left and EPA plots on the right. The second and third rows are plots for the 1st picks and the 2nd picks, respectively, of both red and blue alliances, with OPR plots on the left and EPA plots on the right.

During the Week 1 Hatboro-Horsham Event, the red alliance won overwhelmingly. For the other three events, higher OPR or EPA of the red alliance members generally leads to higher probability of red alliance winning; higher OPR or EPA of the blue alliance members generally leads to the opposite.

Figure 1: EPA vs OPA as the competition season progress in 2022. Wk1 panel is the FMA Hatboro-Horsham Event. Wk3 panel is the FMA Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event. Wk6 panel is the FMA District Championship. Wk8 panel is the Turing Division competition at World Championship.

Figure 2: Probability of winning by the red alliance vs performance metrics (OPA and EPA) of alliance captains, the 1st picks, and the 2nd picks for 2022 events: a) FMA Hatboro-Horsham Event in Week 1; b) FMA Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event in Week 3; c) FMA District Championship; d) Turing Division competition at World Championship.

2.2 Charged Up: 2023 Season

[Charged Up](#) is the 2023 season game. Its basic goal is to “score cubes and cones into their grids”.

Plots in Figure 3 below are similar to those in Figure 1, but for the 2023 season. The timing of the events is the same as in the previous season. Again, different color dots represent the teams that are alliance captain, the 1st pick, the 2nd pick, and the teams that didn't make the playoff round.

Again, the OPA and EPA scores are largely correlated with each other. As the competition season progresses, both OPA and EPA shifted upper ward, which may reflect team improvement, as well as selection bias in the championship events. This year, there seems to be a separation of a group of good teams from the rest, and less individually dominant teams. Given the fact that, in local district competition events, the same teams from the same schools usually compete in the same events year after year, this may represent some overall improvement within our district.

For Figure 4, it is interesting to note that the overall probability of red alliance winning is reduced in 2023, at least for the three earlier events. This probably reflects a rule change for how the playoff round is organized. Before 2023, the playoff round was a single elimination bracket. For the 2023 season, the playoff format was changed into double elimination bracket to give lower seeded alliances a chance at progressing further in playoffs. Since red is always assigned to the alliance captained by higher seed, this format change reduced overall red alliance winning probability as closer seeded alliances played against each other more often, making the games more interesting and the dataset more informative.

Figure 3: EPA vs OPA as the competition season progress in 2023. Wk1 panel is the FMA Hatboro-Horsham Event. Wk3 panel is the FMA Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event. Wk6 panel is the FMA District Championship. Wk8 panel is the Hopper Division competition at World Championship.

Figure 4: Probability of winning by the red alliance vs performance metrics (OPA and EPA) of alliance captains, the 1st picks, and the 2nd picks for 2023 events: a) FMA Hatboro-Horsham Event in Week 1; b) FMA Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event in Week 3; c) FMA District Championship; d) Hopper Division competition at World Championship.

2. Model Comparison

2.1 Model Description

The probability of winning by the red alliance can be modeled by logistic regression with the performance metric of alliance captains, the 1st picks, and the 2nd picks, as measured by either their OPR or EPA scores. To evaluate the team contributions, the following three models are fitted to each event data using the R function `glm` (generalized linear model with logistic link):

$$\text{glm}(\text{redwin} \sim \text{redCaptain} + \text{BlueCaptain}, \text{family}=\text{binomial}()) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{glm}(\text{redwin} \sim \text{redCaptain} + \text{redPick1} + \text{blueCaptain} + \text{bluePick1}, \text{family}=\text{binomial}()) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{glm}(\text{redwin} \sim \text{redCaptain} + \text{redPick1} + \text{redPick2} + \text{blueCaptain} + \text{bluePick1} + \text{bluePick2}, \text{family}=\text{binomial}()) \quad (3)$$

For each competition event, the total number of matches during the playoff round is around 16. There is not enough sample size to allow hypothesis testing. However, Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) can be used to compare different models from (1) to (3) using either OPA or EPA scores. AIC is defined as

$$AIC = -2 \log(L(\hat{\theta})) + 2k$$

where $L(\hat{\theta})$ is the likelihood and k is the number of parameters in the model. For model (1), (2), and (3), $k = 3, 5, 7$, respectively. Due to the relatively small size for each event, the second-order information criteria AIC_c is used, which is defined as

$$AIC_c = AIC + \frac{2k(k+1)}{n-k-1}$$

where n is the total number of playoff matches in each competition event (Burnham and Anderson 2010, page 66).

The model with smallest AIC_c is the most parsimonious model among the candidate model set. And the difference $\Delta = AIC_c - \min(AIC_c)$ is related to how plausible each model is given the data. In fact, the Akaike Weights (Burnham and Anderson 2010, page 75), defined below, is the relative likelihood of the model given the data and the candidate model set.

$$\frac{\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\Delta_i\right)}{\sum_{r=1}^R \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\Delta_r\right)}$$

2.2 Results and Discussion

Table 1 below lists the Akaike weights for each event. Alliance captains' performances are the most important factor. The 2nd picks don't matter, and the 1st pick may matter depending on the event or performance metric used. EPA and OPR are about the same in explaining outcomes as performance metrics.

Table 1: Akaike Weights for Each Competition Event

Event	Model	2022		2023	
		OPR	EPA	OPR	EPA
FMA Hatboro-Horsham Event	(1)	0.49	0.49	0.10	0.10
	(2)	0.01	0.01	0.25	0.25
	(3)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
FMA Springside Chestnut Hill Academy Event	(1)	0.22	0.75	0.47	0.43
	(2)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.08
	(3)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
FMA District Championship	(1)	0.34	0.45	0.04	0.93
	(2)	0.10	0.10	0.02	0.02
	(3)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Division event at FIRST World Championship	(1)	0.64	0.31	0.11	0.33
	(2)	0.03	0.03	0.55	0.02
	(3)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

References

Burnham, K.P. and Anderson, D. R. (2010) Model Selection and Multimodel Inference, A Practical Information-Theoretic Approach, 2nd ed., New York: Springer